

Apparent molar volumes and viscosities of aqueous solutions of uni-univalent mixed electrolytes with a common cation at different temperatures

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Abstract : Apparent molar volumes (V_{ϕ}) and viscosities (η) of aqueous solutions of uni-univalent mixed electrolytes with a common cation (Na^+) have been determined as a function of fraction of ionic strength due to the first electrolyte in the mixture of two electrolytes at 293.15, 303.15 and 313.15 K. The activation thermodynamic quantities ($\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$, $\Delta S_2^{0\#}$ and $\Delta H_2^{0\#}$) of viscous flow for aqueous solutions of uni-univalent mixed electrolyte systems have been calculated at 293.15, 303.15 and 313.15 K. The results of the study reveal that the uni-univalent mixed electrolytes behave as structure makers in aqueous solutions. The conclusions in regard to ion-ion and ion-solvent interactions have been derived on the basis of the values of constants of Masson's and Jones-Dole equations.

Keywords : Molar volumes, viscosity, mixed electrolyte.

Mixed electrolytes are very important in that they are found in numerous processes in chemical industry. They occur in enormous quantities in water of the oceans and have an important role in the physiological process of body fluids and cell equilibria¹. Studies on viscosity of ionic solutions are of great help in characterizing the structure properties of solutions. Various types of interactions exist between the ions in solutions and of these ion-ion and ion-solvent interactions are of current interest in all the branches of Chemistry. These interactions help in better understanding of the nature of solute and solvent i.e. whether the solute modifies or distorts the structure of solvent²⁻⁹. Patil and co-workers¹⁰ have determined viscosities and densities for aqueous binary solutions involving tetraalkyl ammonium bromide salts and CsBr and LiBr. By using viscosity and density data and the appropriate thermodynamic equations the parameters like limiting apparent molar volume (V_{ϕ}^0) and viscosity B -coefficient have been computed.

Patil *et al.*¹¹ have measured viscosities of aqueous mixed electrolyte solutions involving the systems : KBr-NaBr, KBr-Bu₄NBr, NaCl-NaBr and NaCl-Bu₄NBr at constant ionic strengths, 0.2, 0.5 and 1.0 with varying elec-

trolyte mole fractions. The viscosity data have been used to calculate viscosity B -coefficients of the total electrolyte as a function of solute mole fraction. The results have been explained in terms of cation-cation, anion-anion interactions and the specific structural interactions with solvent water. Pandey and Yasmin¹² have experimentally measured the viscosities and densities of aqueous binary electrolytic solutions at different molalities at 298.15 K and reported relative viscosities, apparent molar volumes and free energy of activation. Parmar and Dhiman¹³ have determined partial molar volumes of some mineral salts viz. sodium sulphate, potassium sulphate, ammonium sulphate and magnesium sulphate in binary aqueous solutions of urea at different temperatures and mineral salts concentrations from density measurements. The data have been evaluated by using Masson equation¹⁴ and the obtained parameters have been interpreted in terms of ion-solvent and ion-ion interactions. The partial molar volumes vary with temperature as a power series of temperature. Structure making/breaking capacities of the mineral salts have been inferred from the sign of $(\partial^2\phi_v^0/\partial T^2)_p$, which shows that ammonium sulphate and magnesium sulphate act as structure breakers while so-

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dium sulphate and potassium sulphate act as structure makers/promoters. Jha *et al.*¹⁵ have determined densities and viscosities of some alkali metal chlorides in tetrahydrofuran + water mixtures at different concentrations and temperatures. The ion-ion and ion-solvent interactions have been discussed in the light of the interaction parameters of Masson¹⁴ and Jones-Dole¹⁶ equations.

From the above survey of literature, it appears that so far as the viscometric and thermodynamic studies of the solutions of mixed electrolyte systems are concerned only a few references are available in the literature to this effect. Hence, the present study on the determination of viscosities and apparent molar volumes of aqueous solutions of the following uni-univalent mixed electrolytes, with Na⁺ as the common cation, has been undertaken : NaCl + NaBr; NaCl + NaNO₃; CH₃COONa + NaCl; NaNO₃ + NaBr; CH₃COONa + NaBr and CH₃COONa + NaNO₃.

The main thrust of this study is to determine the viscosities of solutions of uni-univalent mixed electrolyte systems, at different ionic strengths, as a function of fraction of ionic strength due to first electrolyte in the mixture of two electrolytes at different temperatures. The viscosity data will be used to calculate *A*- and *B*-coefficients of Jones-Dole¹⁶ equation. From the values of viscosity *A*- and *B*-coefficients conclusions will be derived in regard to ion-ion and ion-solvent interactions. The results of viscometric studies would be supplemented by thermodynamic investigation, which involves the determination of apparent molar volumes (*V_φ*) from density and concentration data of solutions of mixed electrolyte systems at different temperatures. From the values of apparent molar volumes as a function of the fraction of the ionic strength due to the first electrolyte in the mixture of two electrolytes, limiting apparent volume (*V_φ⁰*) and *S_v* would be determined at different temperatures with a view to deriving conclusions in regard to the nature and magnitude of ion-solvent and ion-ion interactions. Further by determining the free energy of activation of viscous flow, *μ₁^{0#}* and *μ₂^{0#}*, per mole of solvent (water) and solute (mixed electrolyte systems) respectively, the structure-making or structure-breaking capacity in mixed electrolyte system will be ascertained.

The above study has been undertaken in the light of

following aspects : (i) Determination of densities and viscosities of aqueous solutions of above mentioned uni-univalent mixed electrolytes at different temperatures (293.15, 303.15 and 313.15 ± 0.01 K) as a function of *y*, the fraction of ionic strength due to the first electrolyte in the mixture of two electrolytes, keeping the ionic strength (*I*) constant at three different values viz. 1.0, 1.5 and 2.0; (ii) Analysis of viscosity data in the light of the modified form of Jones-Dole equation and determination of the values of the coefficients *A* and *B* at different ionic strengths and temperatures; (iii) Determination of apparent molar volumes from the density-concentration data as a function of *y* at different temperatures and then to obtain the values of *V_φ⁰* and *S_v* of the modified form of Masson's equation; (iv) Determination of free energies of activation of viscous flow, *Δμ₁^{0#}* and *Δμ₂^{0#}* per mole of solvent (water) and solute (mixed electrolytes) respectively at different ionic strengths and temperatures; and also determination of entropy and enthalpy of activation of viscous flow under these experimental conditions; and (v) Ascertaining the structure-making or structure-breaking capacities of the uni-univalent mixed electrolyte systems in aqueous medium.

Results and discussion

The nature of ion-ion and ion-solvent interactions in a system involving single electrolyte is studied by applying Jones-Dole equation¹⁶

$$\frac{\eta}{\eta_0} = \eta_{\text{rel}} = 1 + A\sqrt{C} + BC \quad (1)$$

$$\text{or } (\eta_{\text{rel}} - 1) = A\sqrt{C} + BC \quad (2)$$

$$\text{or } \frac{\eta_{\text{rel}} - 1}{\sqrt{C}} = A + B\sqrt{C} \quad (3)$$

where η and η_0 are the viscosities of the solution and solvent respectively. The coefficient *A* in this equation is a measure of ion-ion interaction, whereas the coefficient *B* is a measure of ion-solvent interaction.

The relative viscosity of the mixed electrolyte system can be expressed in terms of *y*, the fraction of ionic strength due to the first electrolyte in a mixture of two electrolytes. Thus replacing *C* by *y*, Jones-Dole equation becomes

$$\frac{\eta}{\eta_0} = \eta_{\text{rel}} = 1 + A\sqrt{y} + By \quad (4)$$

$$\text{or } (\eta_{\text{rel}} - 1) = A\sqrt{y} + By \quad (5)$$

$$\text{or } \frac{\eta_{\text{rel}} - 1}{\sqrt{y}} = A + B\sqrt{y} \quad (6)$$

The values of A and B have been obtained from the linear plots of $(\eta_{\text{rel}} - 1)/\sqrt{y}$ versus \sqrt{y} (vide representative Figs. 1–3) by computerized least squares fit of the above eq. (6) and listed in Table 1 along with the ' σ ' (standard deviation) of the fit. It is seen that the values of coefficient A are negative in each case at different ionic strengths and temperatures which indicate the presence of weak ion-ion interactions in all the mixed electrolyte systems. On the other hand, the values of coefficient B are positive, which show the presence of strong ion-solvent interactions. Further, it is seen that the values of B -coefficient become larger with the increase of ionic strength as well

Fig. 1. Variation of $(\eta_{\text{rel}} - 1)/\sqrt{y}$ with \sqrt{y} for aqueous solutions of NaCl + NaBr ($I = 1.0$) at different temperatures : (□) 293.15 K; (Δ) 303.15 K; (○) 313.15 K.

as with the rise of temperature, which indicate that ion-solvent interactions become stronger at higher ionic strength and temperature. The positive values of coefficient B also indicate¹⁷ that the uni-univalent mixed electrolytes behave as structure-makers in aqueous medium.

The apparent molar volume (V_ϕ) of aqueous solutions of uni-univalent mixed electrolytes was determined from density and concentration data at different temperatures, using the following equation¹⁸.

$$V_\phi = \frac{1000(\rho_0 - \rho)}{C\rho_0} + \frac{\bar{M}}{\rho_0} \quad (7)$$

where ρ_0 and ρ are densities of solvent and solutions respectively and C is the total molarity of the mixed electrolyte system. \bar{M} is the effective molecular weight of the mixed electrolyte system given by following equation

$$\bar{M} = \frac{n_1M_1 + n_2M_2}{n_1 + n_2} \quad (8)$$

where n_1 and n_2 are the number of moles and M_1 and M_2 are the molecular weights of first and second electrolyte respectively.

For a single electrolyte system the concentration dependence of apparent molar volume V_ϕ is given by the Masson's equation¹⁴

$$V_\phi = V_\phi^0 + S_v\sqrt{C} \quad (9)$$

where V_ϕ^0 is called the limiting apparent molar volume and is equal to the partial molar volume (\bar{V}_2^0) of the solute at infinite dilution which is related to ion-solvent interaction and S_v is the experimental slope, dependent on charge and type of the electrolyte and is related to ion-ion interaction.

However, in the present study of uni-univalent mixed electrolyte systems the plots of V_ϕ versus y are linear (vide representative Figs. 4–6), while those of V_ϕ versus \sqrt{y} are non-linear (vide representative Figs. 7–9). From this it follows that in solutions of uni-univalent mixed electrolyte systems, the variation of V_ϕ with y i.e. the fraction of the ionic strength due to the first electrolyte in the mixture of two electrolytes, at different temperatures is linear and is governed by the following modified form of Masson's equation

Fig. 2. Variation of $(\eta_{rel} - 1)/\sqrt{y}$ with \sqrt{y} for aqueous solutions of NaCl + NaBr ($I = 1.5$) at different temperatures : (□) 293.15 K; (Δ) 303.15 K; (○) 313.15 K.

Fig. 3. Variation of $(\eta_{rel} - 1)/\sqrt{y}$ with \sqrt{y} for aqueous solutions of NaCl + NaBr ($I = 2.0$) at different temperatures : (□) 293.15 K; (Δ) 303.15 K; (○) 313.15 K.

Table 1. Values of constants A and B of Jones-Dole equation for uni-univalent mixed electrolyte systems in aqueous medium at different ionic strengths (I) and temperatures

Mixed electrolyte system	Ionic strength (I)								
	A ($\text{dm}^{3/2} \text{mol}^{-1/2}$)			B ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$)			σ^*		
	1.0	1.50	2.00	1.0	1.50	2.00	1.0	1.50	2.00
	Temp. 293.15 K								
NaCl + NaBr	-0.2251	-0.2322	-0.2441	0.2447	0.4600	0.7558	0.009	0.011	0.010
NaCl + NaNO ₃	-0.0749	-0.0833	-0.1084	0.2272	0.2727	0.3895	0.008	0.009	0.011
CH ₃ COONa + NaCl	-0.0841	-0.0984	-0.1037	1.2268	1.5078	1.8840	0.007	0.012	0.008
NaNO ₃ + NaBr	-0.2185	-0.2294	-0.3060	0.2279	0.4352	0.5899	0.009	0.007	0.008
CH ₃ COONa + NaBr	-0.0168	-0.0762	-0.1410	0.4717	0.5820	1.2245	0.007	0.009	0.009
CH ₃ COONa + NaNO ₃	-0.0590	-0.0898	-0.1709	0.7059	0.8998	1.1858	0.009	0.006	0.009
	Temp. 303.15 K								
NaCl + NaBr	-0.2268	-0.2686	-0.3016	0.3221	0.5932	0.7974	0.010	0.009	0.012
NaCl + NaNO ₃	-0.1141	-0.1373	-0.1829	0.2494	0.3796	0.6977	0.012	0.008	0.009
CH ₃ COONa + NaCl	-0.0989	-0.1007	-0.1218	1.5430	1.6680	1.9781	0.008	0.009	0.012
NaNO ₃ + NaBr	-0.3173	-0.3276	-0.3301	0.4160	0.5722	0.6944	0.009	0.010	0.008
CH ₃ COONa + NaBr	-0.0579	-0.1597	-0.2477	0.6691	0.7475	1.4306	0.008	0.012	0.009
CH ₃ COONa + NaNO ₃	-0.1168	-0.1704	-0.3743	0.8921	1.2143	2.0144	0.012	0.009	0.011

	Temp. 313.15 K								
NaCl + NaBr	-0.2275	-0.2974	-0.4131	0.3595	0.6566	0.8617	0.006	0.011	0.013
NaCl + NaNO ₃	-0.1210	-0.1426	-0.3897	0.3419	0.4995	0.7816	0.008	0.010	0.010
CH ₃ COONa + NaCl	-0.1023	-0.1237	-0.1918	1.6322	1.7515	1.9813	0.004	0.009	0.011
NaNO ₃ + NaBr	-0.4016	-0.3863	-0.3938	0.4651	0.6785	0.7588	0.013	0.008	0.013
CH ₃ COONa + NaBr	-0.1171	-0.1930	-0.2527	0.7838	0.8030	1.5918	0.006	0.012	0.012
CH ₃ COONa + NaNO ₃	-0.2016	-0.2723	-0.3783	0.9215	1.5349	2.5248	0.013	0.010	0.013

*Standard deviation of the fit.

$$V_{\phi} = V_{\phi}^0 + S_V y \quad (10)$$

From the intercept and slope of the linear plots of V_{ϕ} versus y (vide representative Figs. 4–6) the values of V_{ϕ}^0 and S_V have been obtained by the method of least squares fit of eq. (10) and presented in Table 2 along with the ' σ ' of the fit. A perusal of this Table shows that the values of V_{ϕ}^0 are positive for all the uni-univalent mixed electrolytes, which indicate¹³ the presence of strong ion-solvent interactions in the aqueous solutions of uni-univalent mixed

electrolytes. It is also observed that with the increase of the ionic strength and rise of temperature, the values of V_{ϕ}^0 become more positive which suggest that under these experimental conditions the ion-solvent interactions become more stronger. This may be attributed to the increased solvation of the ions. A perusal of Table 2 also shows that the values of S_V are negative and are rendered increasingly more negative with the increase of ionic strength of the solutions of uni-univalent mixed electro-

Fig. 4. Variation of V_{ϕ} with y for aqueous solutions of NaCl + NaBr ($I = 1.0$) at different temperatures : (\square) 293.15 K; (Δ) 303.15 K; (\circ) 313.15 K.

Fig. 5. Variation of V_{ϕ} with y for aqueous solutions of NaCl + NaBr ($I = 1.5$) at different temperatures : (\square) 293.15 K; (Δ) 303.15 K; (\circ) 313.15 K.

lytes as well as with the rise of temperature. This suggests the presence of weak ion-ion interactions in the aqueous solutions of these mixed electrolytes and that the ion-ion interactions are further weakened with the increase of ionic strength and the rise of temperature.

Thus, the conclusions in regard to the presence of weak ion-ion interactions and strong ion-solvent interactions arrived at on the basis of viscosity and apparent molar volume data are identical.

The viscosity data have been analyzed on the basis of transition state treatment of relative viscosity of electrolytic solutions as suggested by Feakins *et al.*¹⁹. The coefficient B of the Jones-Dole equation is related to the free energy of activation by the following equation.

$$B = \frac{\bar{V}_1^0 - \bar{V}_2^0}{1000} + \frac{\bar{V}_1^0}{1000} [(\Delta\mu_2^{0\#} - \Delta\mu_1^{0\#})/RT] \quad (11)$$

where \bar{V}_1^0 is the mean volume of the solvent and \bar{V}_2^0 is the partial molar volume of the solute, $\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$ is free en-

ergy of activation per mole of the pure solvent and $\mu_2^{0\#}$ is the free energy of activation per mole of solute. These were calculated with the help of following equations :

$$\Delta\mu_1^{0\#} = RT \ln (\eta_0 \bar{V}_1^0/hN) \quad (12)$$

$$\Delta\mu_2^{0\#} = \Delta\mu_1^{0\#} + \frac{RT}{\bar{V}_1^0} [1000B - (\bar{V}_1^0 - \bar{V}_2^0)] \quad (13)$$

where h is the Planck constant, N is the Avogadro number, η_0 is the viscosity of the solvent, R is the gas constant and T is the absolute temperature.

The entropy of activation of viscous flow of different mixed electrolyte systems was obtained from the following relation¹⁹.

$$d(\Delta\mu_2^{0\#})/dT = -\Delta S_2^{0\#} \quad (14)$$

The enthalpy of activation $\Delta H_2^{0\#}$ was calculated with the help of the following relation^{19,20},

$$\Delta H_2^{0\#} = \Delta\mu_2^{0\#} + T\Delta S_2^{0\#} \quad (15)$$

Fig. 6. Variation of V_ϕ with y for aqueous solutions of NaCl + NaBr ($I = 2.0$) at different temperatures : (\square) 293.15 K; (Δ) 303.15 K; (\circ) 313.15 K.

Fig. 7. Variation of V_ϕ with \sqrt{y} for aqueous solutions of NaCl + NaBr ($I = 1.0$) at different temperatures : (\square) 293.15 K; (Δ) 303.15 K; (\circ) 313.15 K.

Fig. 8. Variation of V_{ϕ} with \sqrt{I} for aqueous solutions of NaCl + NaBr ($I = 1.5$) at different temperatures : (\square) 293.15 K; (Δ) 303.15 K; (\circ) 313.15 K.

Fig. 9. Variation of V_{ϕ} with \sqrt{I} for aqueous solutions of NaCl + NaBr ($I = 2.0$) at different temperatures : (\square) 293.15 K; (Δ) 303.15 K; (\circ) 313.15 K.

Table 2. Values of limiting apparent molar volume (V_{ϕ}^0) and experimental slope (S_v) of uni-univalent mixed electrolyte systems in aqueous medium at different ionic strengths (I) and temperatures

Mixed electrolyte system	Ionic strength (I)								
	V_{ϕ}^0 ($\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$)			S_v ($\text{cm}^3 \text{dm}^{3/2} \text{mol}^{-3/2}$)			σ^*		
	1.0	1.50	2.00	1.0	1.50	2.00	1.0	1.50	2.00
	Temp. 293.15 K								
NaCl + NaBr	45.99	46.91	47.15	-25.74	-25.89	-29.98	0.012	0.013	0.012
NaCl + NaNO ₃	26.70	27.77	31.63	-7.26	-7.49	-14.08	0.011	0.012	0.013
CH ₃ COONa + NaCl	96.21	98.41	99.35	-84.11	-85.69	-86.48	0.018	0.012	0.014
NaNO ₃ + NaBr	46.25	47.53	48.73	-19.95	-20.36	-20.90	0.011	0.011	0.011
CH ₃ COONa + NaBr	90.89	93.21	94.67	-44.22	-47.26	-52.47	0.010	0.012	0.013
CH ₃ COONa + NaNO ₃	89.44	90.37	91.21	-50.14	-58.24	-59.21	0.013	0.011	0.014
	Temp. 303.15 K								
NaCl + NaBr	47.56	49.61	50.26	-27.08	-28.41	-30.25	0.010	0.012	0.011
NaCl + NaNO ₃	29.98	31.10	32.28	-9.61	-12.09	-17.40	0.012	0.014	0.013
CH ₃ COONa + NaCl	98.97	99.81	102.91	-85.23	-88.23	-89.93	0.011	0.010	0.012
NaNO ₃ + NaBr	47.97	48.66	50.33	-21.31	-21.94	-21.00	0.012	0.013	0.014
CH ₃ COONa + NaBr	92.19	94.05	98.60	-54.91	-56.15	-61.67	0.013	0.012	0.014
CH ₃ COONa + NaNO ₃	90.37	91.36	96.64	-57.51	-61.77	-66.64	0.010	0.011	0.012

		Temp. 313.15 K							
NaCl + NaBr	49.64	50.60	51.28	-28.28	-28.81	-33.49	0.010	0.013	0.012
NaCl + NaNO ₃	32.02	33.15	33.39	-9.89	-12.14	-17.67	0.011	0.012	0.010
CH ₃ COONa + NaCl	101.60	102.14	104.15	-86.90	-89.97	-90.68	0.010	0.013	0.011
NaNO ₃ + NaBr	50.22	51.25	51.85	-22.17	-22.36	-23.03	0.012	0.011	0.013
CH ₃ COONa + NaBr	98.48	101.67	102.08	-57.94	-61.83	-66.28	0.011	0.012	0.014
CH ₃ COONa + NaNO ₃	91.30	94.38	103.54	-64.03	-65.05	-75.87	0.013	0.012	0.011

*Standard Deviation of the fit.

Table 3. Free energy of activation for viscous flow ($\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$) of water at different temperatures

Temp. (K)	$\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)
293.15	20.54
303.15	20.67
313.15	20.84

Table 4. Values of free energy of activation for viscous flow, $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$ of uni-univalent mixed electrolyte systems in aqueous medium at different ionic strength (*I*) and temperatures

Mixed electrolyte system	$\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹) Ionic strength (<i>I</i>)		
	1.0	1.5	2.0
Temp. 293.15 K			
NaCl + NaBr	36.87	66.10	106.11
NaCl + NaNO ₃	31.90	38.20	54.50
CH ₃ COONa + NaCl	176.40	214.68	265.65
NaNO ₃ + NaBr	34.64	62.83	83.90
CH ₃ COONa + NaBr	73.62	88.84	175.88
CH ₃ COONa + NaNO ₃	105.08	131.91	170.20
Temp. 303.15 K			
NaCl + NaBr	49.04	86.99	115.67
NaCl + NaNO ₃	36.45	54.76	99.27
CH ₃ COONa + NaCl	226.41	243.96	287.62
NaNO ₃ + NaBr	62.18	84.06	101.32
CH ₃ COONa + NaBr	103.63	104.32	210.69
CH ₃ COONa + NaNO ₃	134.47	179.44	291.81
Temp. 313.15 K			
NaCl + NaBr	56.14	98.91	128.44
NaCl + NaNO ₃	51.08	73.86	114.38
CH ₃ COONa + NaCl	246.24	263.44	296.71
NaNO ₃ + NaBr	71.37	102.15	113.76
CH ₃ COONa + NaBr	124.04	127.25	240.51
CH ₃ COONa + NaNO ₃	144.25	231.24	298.56

The free energies of activation of viscous flow $\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$ and $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$ per mole of solvent (water) and solute (mixed electrolyte systems) respectively have been obtained at different temperatures and the values are listed in Tables 3 and 4. It is seen that the values of $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$ are much larger than the values of $\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$. Further, the values of $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$ tend to increase with the rise in ionic strength of the solutions of mixed electrolytes. From this it follows that the process of viscous flow becomes more difficult at higher ionic strengths, which may be attributed to strong ion-solvent interactions due to the increased solvation of the mixed electrolytes in aqueous medium. Further, it is seen that for all the uni-univalent mixed electrolytes ($\mu_2^{0\#} - \mu_1^{0\#}$) > 0. This shows^{19,21,22} that the uni-univalent mixed electrolytes used in the present study behave as structure-makers in aqueous medium.

The values of entropy ($\Delta S_2^{0\#}$) and enthalpy ($\Delta H_2^{0\#}$) of activation of viscous flow for the aqueous solutions of uni-univalent mixed electrolytes at different temperatures have been obtained (vide eqs. (14) and (15)) and listed in Table 5. It is seen that the values of $T\Delta S_2^{0\#}$ and $T\Delta H_2^{0\#}$ are negative in each case which suggest that the transition state is associated with bond making and increase in order. Although a detailed mechanism for this cannot be easily advanced, it may be suggested that the slip-plane is in the disordered state¹⁹.

Experimental

All the uni-univalent electrolytes, i.e. NaCl, NaBr, NaNO₃ and CH₃COONa, were of analytical reagent grade (B.D.H.), and were used after drying in a vacuum oven at 110 °C for 10 to 12 h. The standard stock solutions of these electrolytes were prepared in double distilled water (specific conductivity $\sim 10^{-6}$ Ω⁻¹ cm⁻¹). The solutions

Table 5. Values of entropy of activation ($T\Delta S_2^{\ddagger}$) and enthalpy of activation (ΔH_2^{\ddagger}) viscous flow for uni-univalent mixed electrolyte systems in aqueous media at different ionic strengths (I) and temperatures

Mixed electrolyte system	Ionic strength (I)					
	$T\Delta S_2^{\ddagger}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)			ΔH_2^{\ddagger} (kJ mol ⁻¹)		
	1.0	1.50	2.00	1.0	1.5	2.0
	Temp. 293.15 K					
NaCl + NaBr	-282.33	-480.98	-327.34	-245.46	-414.88	-221.23
NaCl + NaNO ₃	-281.12	-522.77	-877.65	-249.22	-484.58	-823.15
CH ₃ COONa + NaCl	-1023.72	-714.75	-455.23	-847.31	-500.08	-189.58
NaNO ₃ + NaBr	-538.47	-576.31	-437.63	-503.83	-513.48	-353.73
CH ₃ COONa + NaBr	-738.97	-562.95	-947.35	-665.35	-474.11	-771.47
CH ₃ COONa + NaNO ₃	-574.07	-1455.97	-1881.42	-468.99	-1324.06	-1711.22
	Temp. 303.15 K					
NaCl + NaBr	-291.96	-497.38	-338.51	-242.93	-410.39	-222.84
NaCl + NaNO ₃	-290.71	-540.60	-907.59	-254.27	-485.85	-808.32
CH ₃ COONa + NaCl	-1058.64	-739.14	-470.76	-832.23	-495.18	-183.14
NaNO ₃ + NaBr	-556.84	-595.97	-452.56	-494.65	-511.92	-351.23
CH ₃ COONa + NaBr	-764.18	-582.15	-979.67	-660.54	-477.83	-768.98
CH ₃ COONa + NaNO ₃	-593.66	-1505.64	-1945.60	-459.19	-1326.20	-1653.79
	Temp. 313.15 K					
NaCl + NaBr	-301.59	-513.79	-349.68	-245.46	-414.88	-221.23
NaCl + NaNO ₃	-300.30	-558.44	-937.53	-249.22	-484.58	-823.15
CH ₃ COONa + NaCl	-1093.56	-763.52	-486.29	-847.31	-500.08	-189.58
NaNO ₃ + NaBr	-575.20	-615.63	-467.49	-503.83	-513.48	-353.73
CH ₃ COONa + NaBr	-789.39	-601.36	-1011.99	-665.35	-474.11	-771.47
CH ₃ COONa + NaNO ₃	-613.24	-1555.30	-2009.78	-468.99	-1324.06	-1711.22

of mixed electrolyte systems of different compositions were prepared by mixing calculated volumes of the solutions of individual electrolytes from their standard stock solutions in a measuring flask, such that the ionic strength (I) of mixed electrolytes system was kept constant at $I = 1.0, 1.5$ and 2.0 .

Densities were measured by using 5 ml pycnometers. The volumes of the pycnometers were calibrated with deionised and doubly distilled water at 293.15, 303.15, 313.15 K. The densities of electrolyte solutions were determined from the mass of the solution in the pycnometer after reaching thermal equilibrium with a water bath at the studied temperatures. A Mettler PM-200 electronic balance with an accuracy of ± 0.0001 g was used for the mass determination.

Viscosities were measured with a calibrated U-type Ostwald viscometer of the British Standard Institution with sufficiently long efflux time to avoid kinetic energy correction. The provided calibrated constants were checked

with water, ethanol and hexane. Temperatures were controlled by a thermostatic water bath fluctuating to ± 0.01 K. The uncertainty of calculated absolute viscosities of the solutions was $\pm 1 \times 10^{-4}$ mPa.s.

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